

Triangular Neutrosophic Fuzzy Reliability Assessment of a Coal Ash Handling System in Thermal Power Plant

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Abstract : The fundamental role of reliability in the coal ash handling system is to improve the overall performance of the system over a specific period without any failure. A coal ash handling system is a complicated structure with five subsystems connected in series configuration. In these two subsystems, namely Electrostatic Preceptor subsystem and Fly Ash Silo Store Subsystem are configured into parallel redundancy. Due to the complexity of modern approaches and fault tree analysis systems, the conventional approaches like Markov birth- death process, semi-Markov have failed to deal with data like incompleteness, inconsistency, and uncertainty. The main objective of the present study is to introduce a novel approach to calculate the reliability of a coal ash handling system in a thermal power plant using the universal generating function. Moreover, the fuzzy Neutrosophic method like triangular Neutrosophic fuzzy numbers with Weibull distribution is used to analyze the fuzzy variables and evaluate the system's performance by offering reliable results in three dimensions: truth, indeterminacy, and false membership functions. The results highlighted the behavior of the fuzzy reliability in the coal ash handling unit under various shape parameters λ ($\lambda=0.5, 0.7, \text{ and } 1$) at discrete time intervals t ($t= 0, 5, \text{ and } 10$). Also, for better clarity the results of fuzzy Neutrosophic reliability are presented graphically. That shows the highest achieved reliability of the coal ash handling system is 0.999965. The outcomes of these studies will serve as realistic guidance for engineers to solve complex reliability problems in real-world scenarios.

Keywords : Coal ash handling system, Universal generating function (UGF), Triangular Neutrosophic number (TNN), sustainable manufacturing system

Abbreviations

UGF	Universal generating function
IFS	Intuitionistic fuzzy set
NFS	Neutrosophic fuzzy sets
TNN	Triangular Neutrosophic number (TNN)
SVTNN	Single valued triangular Neutrosophic number
NWD	Neutrosophic Weibull distribution

1. Introduction

The need for reliable and consistent thermal power plants is increasing over time with the expansion of industries. Environmentally, these plants face issues due to particle pollution, greenhouse emissions, handling by products like fly and bottom ash, etc. So, the coal ash handling system has become an important factor in thermal power plants as this system performs a vital role in managing the exhaust products generated by the combustion of coal. A reliable coal ash handling system performs a crucial role in any plant as it ensures safe operation, plant availability, unplanned shutdowns and adherence to regulations related to the environment. Arora and Kumar [1] derived a stochastic model for computing steady - state availability in a coal ash handling system and suggested their maintenance schedule in a thermal power plant. Gupta et al. [11] evaluated the reliability and availability of an ash handling unit in a steam thermal power plant using the Markov birth- death process and probability theory. Kumar and Tiwari [24] evaluated the performance of an ash handling system using a Petri nets-based technique in a coal -based thermal power plant. Saini et al. [26] used inter- valued trapezoidal Neutrosophic numbers to discuss transportation problems during Covid -19 addressing uncertainty and hesitation in real-life conditions. Malik and Tiwari [27] analyzed the maintenance decision and performance ability of a critical subsystem in a coal ash handling unit in a thermal power plant to analyze the system's reliability by conventional engineers, depending on probabilistic methods. These methods fall short sometimes and become complex for real word problems where the input information is inconsistent, inadequate and imprecise.

To overcome these problems, the reliability assessment is continuously moving towards advanced and sophisticated solutions like fuzzy set theory. The fuzzy set theory was first introduced by Zadeh [2]. Further, an extension in fuzzy set theory named (IFS) was discovered by Atanassov [4] that deals with both membership and non-membership functions. IFS focuses on the data on where degrees of membership and non-membership are available. Garg et al.[14] calculated the reliability of an engineering system using a Lamba- tau method and handled the uncertainties of this system using IFS. However, the main drawback of fuzzy sets and IFS is that it does not deal with inconsistency and ambiguous data in the real world because of their inflexible structure. Talaei et al. [23] introduced the structure of intuitionistic fuzzy modules also derived basic properties of it and studied intuitionistic fuzzy homomorphisms between intuitionistic fuzzy modules. Chatterjee and Chakraborty [35] optimized the electrical discharge machine process through combining IF-RAMS and IF-RATMI approaches with IFS.

As a result of this drawback Smarandache [5] introduced NFS as the extension of the traditional crisp set, fuzzy set and intuitionistic IFS. NFS theory deals with distinct degrees of truth, indeterminacy and falsity membership which span between extraordinary intervals $[-]0^{\wedge}, 1^{\wedge}+ [-]$ [. Smarandache [8] generalized the intuitionistic fuzzy set (IFS), paraconsistent set and intuitionistic set into the Neutrosophic set provided by many examples. Shahzadi et al. [17] developed two new algorithms for medical diagnosis using a single-valued Neutrosophic set. Sumathi and Priya [19] used Neutrosophic numbers and their cuts to calculate first-order Neutrosophic ordinary differential equations. Alhasan and Smarandache [21] studied a flexible approach to the special cases and function relationship in Neutrosophic Weibull distribution to deal with the uncertain and indeterminate problems in the field of reliability engineering. Abobala and Ibrahim [22] proposed the basic concept of refined Neutrosophic number theory that included division, divisors, congruencies, and Pell's equation under the refined Neutrosophic ring of integers. Chang [25] introduced a novel approach to calculating the reliability of a milk manufacturing plant with failure data that includes uncertain and inconsistent data. Mondal et al. [29] discussed the safety system in a nuclear power plant under certain conditions using Neutrosophic- based model. Further, to improve the complicated models and adaptability issues,

this NFS has also culminated in various extensions such as single-valued Neutrosophic set (SVNS), inter-valued Neutrosophic set (IVNS), bipolar Neutrosophic set (BNS), refined Neutrosophic set (RNS) and picture Neutrosophic set (PNS). The SVNN are the measurable and restricted alternatives of NFS first developed by Wang et al. [12] are commonly used to merge practical necessities of real time decision support with philosophical comprehensiveness of Neutrosophic reasoning. Chakraborty et al. [18] introduced the concept of Neutrosophic numbers with variations like linear and non-linear generalized triangular Neutrosophic numbers concept for and de-neutrosophication in Neutrosophic numbers for TNN. Kumar et al. [28] discussed uncertainty and imprecise failure data in reliability through the triangular Neutrosophic set and its applications in a gas turbine system. Moreno et al. [30] calculated security measures in information systems through a combined Neutrosophic based framework of multi-attribute decision-making methods TODIM and PROMETHEE. Kumar and Sharma [31] enhanced the allocation reliability in the solid transportation problem and improved the performance of the system by addressing the uncertainties through the approach of Neutrosophic decision-making framework. Srinivas Prabakaran [32] suggested a novel approach to handle unpredictability, inconsistency, and indeterminacy in optimization procedures through triangular fuzzy Neutrosophic assignment problems with TFNNs and a stepwise Neutrosophic method. Lei [33] provided a stratified fuzzy decision-making method using the triangular fuzzy Neutrosophic number GRA (TFNN-GRA) method under the triangular fuzzy Neutrosophic sets (TFNSs) for evaluating engineering procurement construction projects. Thakur et al. [34] introduced correlation and weighted correlation indicators using Probabilistic Single-Valued Neutrosophic Hesitant Fuzzy Sets (PSVNHFSs) to estimate the complexity of decision-making processes. Zhao [36] discovered the role of triangular Neutrosophic set – QUALIFLEX method to assess the dance teaching quality and address the different criteria such as course content, teaching approaches, instructors' skilled capability, and participation of students etc. Chatterjee and Pramanik [37] developed triangular fuzzy numbers, and the Quadri partitioned Neutrosophic set for enhancing the decision-making approaches under uncertainties, also defined theorems related to union, complement and intersection among three triangular fuzzy Quadri partitioned Neutrosophic sets. Yang [38] presented a novel approach to enhance risk management for safety in fabricated residential construction that addressed inconsistency, uncertainty and irregularity in real-life problems. Sun and Liu [39] introduced the triangular fuzzy Neutrosophic number GRA (TFNN-GRA) technique with TFNS for decision making of Multiple-Attribute without prior eight information in information entropy and evaluated the performance of internally cured high-strength concrete. Saini et al. [40] assessed the Neutrosophic fuzzy reliability and mean time to failure of a hydroelectric power plant. The reliability function is derived using the UGF method.

To assess the reliability of the system, this paper discusses the UGF method developed by Ushakov [3]. It helps analyze and develop the performance of models with discrete random variables. This is a new approach that supports a multi-state system that allows all components to function at multiple levels of performance. With better productivity and transparency, this approach is widely used in modeling processes as compared to various other approaches such as the Markov approach, semi-Markov approach etc. Levitin et al. [6] used genetic algorithm with UGF technique for minimizing investment cost and focused on the redundancy optimization problem in the power system. Dingan and Lisnianski [9] derived fuzzy universal generating functions (FUGF) and UGF with a crisp set for the reliability evaluation of a multi-state system (MSSs). Li and Zio [13] discussed universal generating techniques to assess the reliability of distributed generation systems with a multi-state modeling approach. Guilani et al. [15] evaluated non-repairable three-state system reliability and reduced computational time using UGF and the recursive algorithm. Jin et al. [16] proposed method for probabilistic production using UGF in a wind power integrated power system. When et al. [20] used UGF as a reliability evaluation of a compressor in series-parallel multi-state systems of natural gas pipelines.

Based on the above fact and figures it is found that the existing research in the thermal power plant field only depends on the conventional models of reliability like the Markov birth- death process , RAMD indices, fault tree analysis etc. Also, no research has been done for the coal ash handling unit in a Neutrosophic environment. This combined gap highlighted the necessity of a reliability framework for thermal power plants under Neutrosophic environment.

1.1 Novelty of work

This study offers a novel approach for evaluating the following:

- For the first time, the reliability of a coal handling system is calculated using a unique combination of fuzzy Neutrosophic approach with UGF approach.
- Unlike the traditional studies that use basic probabilistic approaches, this study analyzes reliability through the application of TNN coupled with the Weibull distribution for complex systems to deal with uncertainty.
- To facilitate better understanding a graphical representation of TNN is also provided.

1.2 Structure of paper

The present paper is structured into six major sections: section 1 includes the introductory part with literature review and novelty of work. Section 2 discusses some definitions. In section 3 a detailed system description of the coal ash handling system with flow diagram is provided. The methodology and mathematical computation of reliability using the UGF method are discussed in section 4. Section 5 illustrates reliability illustration and numerical results. At the end, Section 6 concludes the work with its advantages.

2. Definitions

2.1 Universal generating function (UGF)

UGF method is the generalized form of Kettelle's Algorithm which is first introduced by Ushakov [3]. It is generally used to calculate the reliability of a system by measuring the performance and reliability of its components. Levitin [7] applied this method to calculate the series-parallel power system availability using multi-level capabilities. In this paper UGF method has been used to calculate the reliability of the coal ash handling system model shown in Figure (1). This UGF method is a special form of the moment generating function that represents the probability distribution of variables by using a polynomial expression. When N is the total possible values x and p_n is the probability of the system then the independent discrete variable of UGF is defined as:

$$u(z) = \sum_{n=1}^N p_n z^{X_n}$$

2.1.1 UGF for series configuration

For the two components 'a' and 'b' the u-functions are u_a and u_b respectively then UGF for series configuration given as follows:

$$u_a(z) \otimes u_b(z) = \sum_{n=1}^{N_i} p_{in} z^{c_{in}} \otimes \sum_{m=1}^{N_j} p_{jm} z^{c_{jm}}$$

$$\Rightarrow \sum_{n=1}^{N_i} \sum_{m=1}^{N_j} p_{in} p_{jm} \mathcal{Z}^{\text{Min}(c_{in}, c_{jm})}$$

Here \otimes denotes the series configuration between $u_a(\mathcal{Z})$ and $u_b(\mathcal{Z})$.

2.1.2 UGF for parallel configuration

For the two components 'a' and 'b' the u-functions are u_a and u_b respectively then UGF for series configuration given as follows:

$$u_a(\mathcal{Z}) \oplus u_b(\mathcal{Z}) = \sum_{n=1}^{N_i} p_{in} \mathcal{Z}^{c_{in}} \oplus \sum_{m=1}^{N_j} p_{jm} \mathcal{Z}^{c_{jm}}$$

$$\Rightarrow \sum_{n=1}^{N_i} \sum_{m=1}^{N_j} p_{in} p_{jm} \mathcal{Z}^{\text{Max}(c_{in}, c_{jm})}$$

Here \oplus denotes the parallel configuration between $u_a(\mathcal{Z})$ and $u_b(\mathcal{Z})$.

2.2 Neutrosophic fuzzy set

Smarandache [5] introduced Neutrosophic fuzzy sets as the extension of traditional crisp sets, fuzzy sets and intuitionistic fuzzy sets. It is developed to solve challenges like ambiguity, uncertainty and indeterminacy for inadequate and insufficient data. Mathematically, a Neutrosophic set \check{N} with a truth membership function $\check{T}_{\check{N}}(\hat{A})$, an indeterminacy Membership function $\check{I}_{\check{N}}(\hat{A})$ and a falsity-membership function $F_{\check{N}}(\hat{A})$ in a universal set \hat{A} is defined as:

$$\check{N} = \{ \langle A, \check{T}_{\check{N}}(\hat{A}), \check{I}_{\check{N}}(\hat{A}), F_{\check{N}}(\hat{A}) \rangle \mid A \in \hat{A} \}$$

here,

$$\begin{aligned} \check{T}_{\check{N}}(\hat{A}) &:]0^-, 1^+[\\ \check{I}_{\check{N}}(\hat{A}) &:]0^-, 1^+[\\ F_{\check{N}}(\hat{A}) &:]0^-, 1^+[\end{aligned}$$

$$\text{and } 0^- \leq \sup \check{T}_{\check{N}}(\hat{A}) + \sup \check{I}_{\check{N}}(\hat{A}) + \sup F_{\check{N}}(\hat{A}) \leq 1^+$$

2.2.1 Triangular Neutrosophic number (TNN)

A TNS is a special type of Neutrosophic set having the membership values of truth, indeterminacy and falsity. Each element of these membership values in the universe of discourse are represented by a triangular-shaped membership function. Mathematically, TNS with a truth membership function $\check{T}_{\check{N}}(\hat{A})$, an indeterminacy membership function $\check{I}_{\check{N}}(\hat{A})$ and a falsity-membership function $F_{\check{N}}(\hat{A})$ in a universe of discourse \hat{A} is represented as follows:

$$\check{N}_{TNS} = \{ \langle A, \check{T}_{\check{N}}(\hat{A}), \check{I}_{\check{N}}(\hat{A}), F_{\check{N}}(\hat{A}) \rangle \mid A \in \hat{A} \}$$

Here, $\check{T}_{\tilde{N}}(\hat{A}), \check{I}_{\tilde{N}}(\hat{A})$ and $F_{\tilde{N}}(\hat{A}) \subseteq [0,1]$

Figure 1 : Graphical representation of triangular Neutrosophic number

2.1.1 Single valued triangular Neutrosophic number (SVTNN)

Smarandache et al. [10] introduced SVTNN which are a specific type of Neutrosophic numbers with the truth, indeterminacy and falsity membership values used in different real time applications. Graphical representation of SVTNN is shown in figure 2:

Figure 2: Graphical representation of SVTNN along with membership values

If $\omega_{\check{N}}(\hat{A})$ is the truth membership function, $\Omega_{\check{N}}(\hat{A})$ is the indeterminacy membership function and $\vartheta_{\check{N}}(\hat{A})$ is the falsity-membership function in a universe of discourse \hat{A} then for $\check{N} = \{\check{p}_1, \check{p}_2, \check{p}_3; \check{r}_1, \check{r}_2, \check{r}_3; \check{s}_1, \check{s}_2, \check{s}_3\}$ the membership functions is defined as:

$$\omega_{\check{N}}(\hat{A}) = \begin{cases} \frac{a - \check{p}_1}{\check{p}_2 - \check{p}_1} & ; \text{ if } \check{p}_1 \leq a < \check{p}_2 \\ 1 & ; \text{ if } a = \check{p}_2 \\ \frac{\check{p}_3 - a}{\check{p}_3 - \check{p}_2} & ; \text{ if } \check{p}_2 < a \leq \check{p}_3 \\ 0 & ; \text{ otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$\Omega_{\check{N}}(\hat{A}) = \begin{cases} \frac{\check{r}_2 - a}{\check{r}_2 - \check{r}_1} & ; \text{ if } \check{r}_1 \leq a \leq \check{r}_2 \\ 0 & ; \text{ if } a = \check{p}_2 \\ \frac{a - \check{r}_2}{\check{r}_3 - \check{r}_2} & ; \text{ if } \check{r}_2 < a \leq \check{r}_3 \\ 1 & ; \text{ otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$\vartheta_{\check{N}}(\hat{A}) = \begin{cases} \frac{\check{s}_2 - a}{\check{s}_2 - \check{s}_1} & ; \text{ if } \check{s}_1 \leq a < \check{s}_2 \\ 0 & ; \text{ if } a = \check{s}_2 \\ \frac{a - \check{s}_2}{\check{s}_3 - \check{s}_2} & ; \text{ if } \check{s}_2 < a \leq \check{s}_3 \\ 1 & ; \text{ otherwise} \end{cases}$$

2.1.1 β – cut :

For all $a \in \beta$ the β -cut for a SVTNN is given as:

$$\check{N}_{\beta-cut} = [\dot{p}_1 + \beta_1(\dot{p}_2 - \dot{p}_1) ; \dot{p}_3 - \beta_2(\dot{p}_3 - \dot{p}_2)]$$

2.1.2 γ – cut :

For all $a \in \gamma$ the γ -cut for a SVTNN is given as:

$$\check{N}_{\gamma-cut} = [\dot{r}_2 - \gamma_1(\dot{r}_2 - \dot{r}_1) ; \dot{r}_2 + \gamma_2(\dot{r}_3 - \dot{r}_2)]$$

2.1.3 δ – cut:

For all $a \in \delta$ the δ -cut for a SVTNN is given as:

$$\check{N}_{\delta-cut} = [\dot{s}_2 - \delta_1(\dot{s}_2 - \dot{s}_1) ; \dot{s}_2 + \delta_2(\dot{s}_3 - \dot{s}_2)]$$

2.3 Weibull distribution

In a reliability analysis of a system where the failure rates are changing continuously with time ,the Weibull distribution plays an important role as a model for time to failure. Usually, it is described by two parameters such as scale and shape parameters, but sometimes it can be extended as three or five parameters Weibull distribution also.

2.3.1 Neutrosophic Weibull distribution (NWD)

The NWD is an extension of a classical Weibull distribution based on three elements: truth (T), indeterminacy (I) and falsity (F). Let X is a continuous variable and there are three parameters such as scale parameter (λ) and shape parameter (μ) then the probability density function (pdf) of a three-parameter Neutrosophic Weibull distribution is:

$$f_N(X) = \frac{\mu_N}{\lambda_N^{\mu_N}} X^{\mu_N-1} e^{-\left(\frac{X}{\lambda_N}\right)^{\mu_N}}$$

Then distribution function is:

$$F_N(X) = 1 - e^{-\left(\frac{X}{\lambda_N}\right)^{\mu_N}} ; \mu_N \leq X$$

The hazard function is :

$$h_N(X) = \mu_N (X)^{\mu_N-1} X^{\left(\frac{\mu_N-1}{\lambda_N}\right)^{\mu_N}} ; \mu_N \leq X$$

2.4 Fuzzy Reliability function

A fuzzy reliability function or survival function $R_N(t)$ with the scale parameter (λ) and the shape parameter (μ) is given by:

$$R_N(t) = \int_t^{\infty} f_N(x) d(x)$$

$$\Rightarrow R_N(t) = \exp\left(-\left(\frac{x}{\lambda_N}\right)^{\mu_N - 1}\right)$$

3. Description of Coal Ash handling system

The coal ash handling system contains five subsystems namely Boiler Furnace Subsystem, Electrostatic Preceptor subsystem, Vessel subsystem, Compressor Transportation Line Subsystem and Ash Silo Subsystem. All five subsystems are connected in a series configuration with each other. The detailed explanation of these subsystems is as follows:

- 3.1 Boiler Furnace Subsystem (A):** A boiler furnace subsystem plays a very crucial role in coal ashes by burning the coal at a high temperature and generated two types of ash such as bottom ash and fly ash. Here, this subsystem contains only single units.
- 3.2 Electrostatic Preceptor (EPS) subsystem (B):** An electrostatic preceptor commonly used to eliminate the fly ash after boiler emissions. This used high voltage electric charges to separates negative charges from the ash particles. This subsystem contains two parallel units, B₁ and B₂.
- 3.3 Vessel subsystem (c) :** A vessel is placed below the EPS subsystem and used as an interim storage and controlling the discharge of the collected ashes. This ash storing capacity depends on the ash lines performance for transporting ash to the silos. This unit contains a single unit.
- 3.4 Compressor Transportation Line Subsystem (D):** A Compressor transportation line is a pipeline system used to move pressurized air or oil from one location to another by controlling the pressure and flow. This subsystem contains single unit here.
- 3.5 Fly Ash Silo Store Subsystem (E):** Fly ash silos store used to collect fly ash coming from electrostatic preceptor and move it to silos for storage fly ash. This subsystem contains two units E₁ and E₂ connected in parallel configuration.

For the successful working of coal ash handling system without interruption it is necessary that all subsystems (namely A,B,C,D and E) which are connected in series configuration work without any failure.

Figure 3: Flow diagram of subsystems of a coal ash handling system

4. Methodology and Mathematical computation

4.1 Methodology

The reliability function of the above model shown in the figure (1) is calculated by the UGF methods using the following steps:

Step 1: Calculate the reliability function $R_i(t)$ for each subsystem.

Step 2: Evaluate the universal generating function (UGF) $u_i(z)$ for each subsystem

Step 3: For the reliability of complete system combines the UGF such

For series configuration : $u_{series}(z) = u_1(z) \times u_2(z) \times \dots \times u_n(z)$

For parallel configuration : $u_{parallel}(z) = 1 - \prod_{i=1}^n (1 - u_i(z))$

Step 4: Using the system's UGF obtain the reliability function taking ($z=1$)

4.2 Mathematical computation

In this section, the mathematical computation for the reliability function has been done. To evaluate the reliability of the model mentioned in figure (1) the UGF approach has been applied. For this purpose, the working states of the systems are represented by 1 and the failed state of the system is represented by 0 respectively and the probabilities of the working state represented P_i and failed state is represented by $(1 - P_i)$. Then the UGF for seven components is generated as follows:

$$\mathbf{A} : u_1(Z) = P_1 Z^1 + (1 - P_1) Z^0 \tag{1}$$

$$\mathbf{B}_1 : u_2(Z) = P_2 Z^1 + (1 - P_2) Z^0 \tag{2}$$

$$\mathbf{B}_2 : u_3(Z) = P_3 Z^1 + (1 - P_3) Z^0 \tag{3}$$

$$\mathbf{C} : u_4(Z) = P_4 Z^1 + (1 - P_4) Z^0 \tag{4}$$

$$\mathbf{D} : u_5(Z) = P_5 Z^1 + (1 - P_5) Z^0 \tag{5}$$

$$\mathbf{E}_1 : u_6(Z) = P_6 Z^1 + (1 - P_6) Z^0 \tag{6}$$

$$\mathbf{E}_2 : u_7(Z) = P_7 Z^1 + (1 - P_7) Z^0 \tag{7}$$

Now, using the equations (2) and (3) calculating UGF as follows:

$$u_{2,3}(Z) = u_2(Z) \oplus u_3(Z)$$

$$\Rightarrow u_{2,3}(Z) = P_2 P_3 Z^1 + P_2 (1 - P_3) Z^1 + P_3 (1 - P_2) Z^1 + (1 - P_2)(1 - P_3) Z^0 \tag{8}$$

$$u_{6,7}(Z) = u_6(Z) \oplus u_7(Z)$$

$$\Rightarrow u_{6,7}(Z) = P_6 P_7 Z^1 + P_6 (1 - P_7) Z^1 + P_7 (1 - P_6) Z^1 + (1 - P_6)(1 - P_7) Z^0 \tag{9}$$

Let, $u_8(Z) = u_{2,3}(Z) \otimes u_{6,7}(Z)$, then UGF is:

$$u(Z) = u_1(Z) \otimes u_4(Z) \otimes u_5(Z) \otimes u_8(Z) \tag{10}$$

Now, after the differentiation of $u(Z)$ with respect to Z and at $Z=1$ the reliability function is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{R} = \mathbf{u}'(Z) = & P_1 P_2 P_3 P_4 P_5 P_6 P_7 + P_1 P_2 P_3 P_4 P_5 P_6 (1 - P_7) + P_1 P_2 P_3 P_4 P_5 P_7 (1 - P_6) + P_1 P_2 P_4 P_5 P_6 P_7 (1 - P_3) \\ & + P_1 P_2 P_4 P_5 P_6 (1 - P_3)(1 - P_7) + P_1 P_2 P_4 P_5 P_7 (1 - P_3)(1 - P_6) + P_1 P_3 P_4 P_5 P_6 P_7 (1 - P_2) + \\ & P_1 P_3 P_4 P_5 P_6 (1 - P_2)(1 - P_7) + P_1 P_3 P_4 P_5 P_7 (1 - P_2)(1 - P_6) \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

Now, taking $P_1 = P_2 = P_3 = P_4 = P_5 = P_6 = P_7 = r$ and solving the equation (11) we get final reliability equation as :

$$R = r^7 - 4r^6 + 4r^7 \tag{12}$$

5. Reliability Evaluation and Numerical Results

5.1 Neutrosophic fuzzy reliability evaluation using SVTNN:

In this section, the truth, indeterminacy and false membership function is derived using the interval arithmetic operation method for SVTNN $\check{N} = \{(9,14,19); (13,14,17); (11,14,18)\}$. By using these membership functions their respective β , γ and δ cuts are calculated as follows:

$$\check{N}_{\beta-cut} = [9 + 5 \beta_1 ; 19 - 5 \beta_2] \tag{13}$$

$$\check{N}_{\gamma-cut} = [14 - \gamma_1 ; 14 + \gamma_2] \tag{14}$$

$$\check{N}_{\delta-cut} = [14 - 3 \delta_1 ; 14 + 4 \delta_2] \tag{15}$$

The reliability function for SVTNN using these β , γ and δ cuts are derived with the help of equation (14) as follows:

$$R_{SVTNN}(\beta_1) = e^{-\left[\left(\frac{t}{9+5\beta_1}\right)^{\xi}\right]^7} - 4 e^{-\left[\left(\frac{t}{9+5\beta_1}\right)^{\xi}\right]^6} + e^{-\left[\left(\frac{t}{9+5\beta_1}\right)^{\xi}\right]^5} \tag{16}$$

$$R_{SVTNN}(\beta_2) = e^{-\left[\left(\frac{t}{19-5\beta_2}\right)^{\xi}\right]^7} - 4 e^{-\left[\left(\frac{t}{19-5\beta_2}\right)^{\xi}\right]^6} + e^{-\left[\left(\frac{t}{19-5\beta_2}\right)^{\xi}\right]^5} \tag{17}$$

$$R_{SVTNN}(\gamma_1) = e^{-\left[\left(\frac{t}{14-\gamma_1}\right)^{\xi}\right]^7} - 4 e^{-\left[\left(\frac{t}{14-\gamma_1}\right)^{\xi}\right]^6} + e^{-\left[\left(\frac{t}{14-\gamma_1}\right)^{\xi}\right]^5} \tag{18}$$

$$R_{SVTNN}(\gamma_2) = e^{-\left[\left(\frac{t}{14+\gamma_2}\right)^{\xi}\right]^7} - 4 e^{-\left[\left(\frac{t}{14+\gamma_2}\right)^{\xi}\right]^6} + e^{-\left[\left(\frac{t}{14+\gamma_2}\right)^{\xi}\right]^5} \tag{19}$$

$$R_{SVTNN}(\delta_1) = e^{-\left[\left(\frac{t}{14-3\delta_1}\right)^{\xi}\right]^7} - 4 e^{-\left[\left(\frac{t}{14-3\delta_1}\right)^{\xi}\right]^6} + e^{-\left[\left(\frac{t}{14-3\delta_1}\right)^{\xi}\right]^5} \tag{20}$$

$$R_{SVTNN}(\delta_2) = e^{-\left[\left(\frac{t}{14+4\delta_2}\right)^{\xi}\right]^7} - 4 e^{-\left[\left(\frac{t}{14+4\delta_2}\right)^{\xi}\right]^6} + e^{-\left[\left(\frac{t}{14+4\delta_2}\right)^{\xi}\right]^5} \tag{21}$$

5.2 Numerical results:

This section includes the numerical results of the Neutrosophic fuzzy reliability of coal ash handling unit. For this purpose, three fixed shape parameters $\xi=0.5,0.7$ and 1 are used and the analysis is performed at different times $t=0, t=5$ and $t=10$ for all three parameters. The values of β , γ and δ range from 0 to 1 with equal distances 0.1 . In tables (1),(2) and (3) the values of fuzzy Neutrosophic reliability are shown for cut values of the truth, indeterminacy and falsity membership function. It is observed that the value of truth membership (ω) at 1 are the same

as the value of indeterminacy (Ω) and falsity (Θ) at 0 at the time $t=0$, $t=5$ and $t=10$ in all three tables.

Table 1: Neutrosophic Reliability at shape parameter $\xi=0.5$ of SVTNN

$\xi=0.5$	t=0			t=5			t=10		
(ω, Ω, Θ) ↓	R(ω_1, ω_2)	R(Ω_1, Ω_2)	R(Θ_1, Θ_2)	R(ω_1, ω_2)	R(Ω_1, Ω_2)	R(Θ_1, Θ_2)	R(ω_1, ω_2)	R(Ω_1, Ω_2)	R(Θ_1, Θ_2)
0	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.943595, 0.990058)	(0.979616, 0.979616)	(0.979616, 0.979616)	(0.888665, 0.980154)	(0.959404, 0.959404)	(0.959404, 0.959404)
0.1	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.950112, 0.989411)	(0.979272, 0.979952)	(0.978559, 0.980915)	(0.901363, 0.978865)	(0.958722, 0.960070)	(0.957310, 0.961979)
0.2	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.955622, 0.988703)	(0.978920, 0.980281)	(0.977424, 0.982100)	(0.912131, 0.977455)	(0.958024, 0.960721)	(0.955061, 0.964330)
0.3	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.960314, 0.987926)	(0.978559, 0.980601)	(0.976202, 0.983184)	(0.921329, 0.975910)	(0.957310, 0.961357)	(0.952641, 0.966482)
0.4	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.964339, 0.987073)	(0.978190, 0.980915)	(0.974885, 0.984178)	(0.929236, 0.974211)	(0.956578, 0.961979)	(0.950036, 0.968457)
0.5	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.967812, 0.986132)	(0.977812, 0.981221)	(0.973463, 0.985091)	(0.936075, 0.972340)	(0.955828, 0.962587)	(0.947224, 0.970271)
0.6	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.970829, 0.985091)	(0.977424, 0.981521)	(0.971925, 0.985932)	(0.942023, 0.970271)	(0.955061, 0.963181)	(0.944186, 0.971942)
0.7	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.973463, 0.983937)	(0.977027, 0.981814)	(0.970258, 0.986707)	(0.947224, 0.967979)	(0.954274, 0.963762)	(0.940897, 0.973485)
0.8	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.975774, 0.982654)	(0.976619, 0.982100)	(0.968450, 0.987424)	(0.951794, 0.965430)	(0.953468, 0.964330)	(0.93733, 0.973485)
0.9	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.977812, 0.981221)	(0.976202, 0.982380)	(0.966483, 0.988087)	(0.955828, 0.962587)	(0.952641, 0.964886)	(0.933455, 0.976231)
1	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.979616, 0.979616)	(0.975774, 0.982654)	(0.964339, 0.988703)	(0.959404, 0.959404)	(0.951794, 0.965430)	(0.929236, 0.977455)

Table 2: Neutrosophic Reliability at shape parameter $\xi=0.7$ of SVTNN

$\xi=0.7$	t=0			t=5			t=10		
(ω, Ω, Θ) ↓	R(ω_1, ω_2)	R(Ω_1, Ω_2)	R(Θ_1, Θ_2)	R(ω_1, ω_2)	R(Ω_1, Ω_2)	R(Θ_1, Θ_2)	R(ω_1, ω_2)	R(Ω_1, Ω_2)	R(Θ_1, Θ_2)
0	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.992724, 0.999414)	(0.998347, 0.998347)	(0.998347, 0.998347)	(0.98546, 0.998827)	(0.996696, 0.996696)	(0.996696, 0.996696)

0.1	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.993923, 0.999358)	(0.998307, 0.998387)	(0.998222, 0.998498)	(0.98786, 0.998716)	(0.996615, 0.979952)	(0.996445, 0.996996)
0.2	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.994879, 0.999295)	(0.998265, 0.998425)	(0.998084, 0.998631)	(0.989768, 0.998590)	(0.996531, 0.980281)	(0.996169, 0.997262)
0.3	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.995650, 0.999224)	(0.998222, 0.998462)	(0.997932, 0.998749)	(0.991307, 0.998449)	(0.996445, 0.980601)	(0.995865, 0.997498)
0.4	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.996278, 0.999144)	(0.998178, 0.998498)	(0.997764, 0.998854)	(0.992561, 0.998288)	(0.996356, 0.980915)	(0.995530, 0.997709)
0.5	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.996794, 0.999053)	(0.998132, 0.998532)	(0.997578, 0.998948)	(0.993591, 0.998106)	(0.996264, 0.981221)	(0.995158, 0.997897)
0.6	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.997221, 0.998948)	(0.998084, 0.998566)	(0.997372, 0.999033)	(0.994445, 0.997897)	(0.996169, 0.981521)	(0.994745, 0.998066)
0.7	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.997578, 0.998829)	(0.998035, 0.998599)	(0.997142, 0.999109)	(0.995158, 0.997658)	(0.996071, 0.981814)	(0.994287, 0.998218)
0.8	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.997878, 0.998691)	(0.997984, 0.998631)	(0.996886, 0.999177)	(0.995757, 0.997383)	(0.995970, 0.982100)	(0.993775, 0.998355)
0.9	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.998132, 0.998532)	(0.997932, 0.998661)	(0.996599, 0.999239)	(0.996264, 0.997065)	(0.995865, 0.982380)	(0.993203, 0.998478)
1	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.998347, 0.998347)	(0.997877, 0.998691)	(0.996278, 0.999295)	(0.996696, 0.996696)	(0.995757, 0.982654)	(0.992561, 0.998590)

Table 3: Neutrosophic Reliability at shape parameter $\xi=1$ of SVTNN

$\xi=1$	t=0			t=5			t=10		
$(\omega, \Omega, \vartheta)$	$R(\omega_1, \omega_2)$	$R(\Omega_1, \Omega_2)$	$R(\vartheta_1, \vartheta_2)$	$R(\omega_1, \omega_2)$	$R(\Omega_1, \Omega_2)$	$R(\vartheta_1, \vartheta_2)$	$R(\omega_1, \omega_2)$	$R(\Omega_1, \Omega_2)$	$R(\vartheta_1, \vartheta_2)$
\downarrow									
0	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.999698, 0.999992)	(0.999965, 0.999965)	(0.999965, 0.999965)	(0.999396, 0.999985)	(0.999931, 0.999931)	(0.999931, 0.999931)
0.1	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.999768, ,0.999991)	(0.999964, 0.999967)	(0.999962, 0.999970)	(0.999536, 0.999983)	(0.999928, 0.999933)	(0.999923, 0.999940)
0.2	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.999820, ,0.999990)	(0.999963, 0.999968)	(0.999957, ,0.999974)	(0.999639, 0.999980)	(0.999926, 0.999936)	(0.999914, 0.999947)
0.3	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.999858, 0.999989)	(0.999962, ,0.999969)	(0.999952, 0.999977)	(0.999716, 0.999977)	(0.999923, 0.999938)	(0.999904, 0.999954)
0.4	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.999887, 0.999987)	(0.999960, 0.999970)	(0.999946, 0.999980)	(0.999774, 0.999973)	(0.999920, 0.999940)	(0.999893, 0.999959)
0.5	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.999909, 0.999985)	(0.999959, 0.999971)	(0.999940, 0.999982)	(0.999818, ,0.999969)	(0.999917, 0.999942)	(0.999879, 0.999964)

0.6	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.999926, 0.999982)	(0.999957, 0.999972)	(0.999932, 0.999984)	(0.999852, 0.999964)	(0.999914, 0.999944)	(0.999864, 0.999968)
0.7	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.999940, 0.999979)	(0.999955, 0.999973)	(0.999923, 0.999986)	(0.999879, 0.999958)	(0.999911, 0.999946)	(0.999846, 0.999972)
0.8	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.999950, 0.999975)	(0.999954, 0.999974)	(0.999913, 0.999987)	(0.999900, 0.999951)	(0.999908, 0.999947)	(0.999826, 0.999975)
0.9	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.999959, 0.999971)	(0.999952, 0.999975)	(0.999901, 0.999989)	(0.999917, 0.999942)	(0.999904, 0.999949)	(0.999802, 0.999978)
1	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.0)	(0.999965, 0.999965)	(0.999950, 0.999975)	(0.999887, 0.999990)	(0.999931, 0.999931)	(0.999900, 0.999951)	(0.999774, 0.999980)

Furthermore, the graphical representation of single valued triangular Neutrosophic number between their six cut values $[9 + 5 \beta_1]$, $[19 - 5 \beta_2]$, $[14 - \gamma_1]$, $[14 + \gamma_2]$, $[14 - 3 \delta_1]$ and $[14 + 4 \delta_2]$ respectively are shown in figure 4.

Figure 4: Graphical representation of Triangular Neutrosophic numbers corresponding to their cut set values

6. Conclusion

In any system's performance, the reliability evaluation plays a very important role as it affects the working efficiency of the system. In this study the fuzzy Neutrosophic reliability of a coal ash handling system is successfully calculated. Here, every fuzzy Neutrosophic variable is represented as SVTNN that follows the Weibull distribution. The reliability function for this is derived using the universal generation function approach. It is apparent from Table (1) that the fuzzy Neutrosophic reliability for SVTNN for all three shape parameters i.e. $\xi=0.5, 0.7$ and 1 at time $t=0$ is (1.0,1.0) for all three membership functions such as truth, indeterminacy and falsity. It is noted that For SVTNN, the highest reliability achieved by the system is 0.999965 for all three membership functions at $t=5$ and shape parameter 0.7. Further, as the time advances $t=0$ to $t=10$ there is a slight decline in the system's reliability that shows a remarkable stability of the coal ash handling system. This sort of stability plays a crucial role by ensuring the smooth and uninterrupted production of power generation with minimal risk of failure. Moreover, the findings of the proposed study highlighted that the fuzzy Neutrosophic methodology performs as a valuable and effective tool for the reliability evaluation of the coal ashes handling system. This approach provides a more comprehensive evaluation by adding uncertainty, indeterminacy and imprecision in the thermal power plant industrial system. Further, this advanced combined approach of Neutrosophic reliability evaluation proposed certain significant advantages in not only thermal power plant industries but also many different industries by providing flexibility in the reliability evaluation in any real-world conditions to solve uncertain, imprecise and conflicting data in various complex engineering applications. The outcome of this study has significant practical uses notably, in the fields where the continuous operations and safety assurance of the system are key components for the reliability evaluation. This research offers more accurate and comprehensive tools for decision makers to calculate reliability and enhance interpretation with the help of a graphical representation of triangular Neutrosophic reliability. Although this research has certain boundaries itself sometime the Neutrosophic membership functions while defining it are dependent upon the expert's judgement. Additionally, when the system has irregular and unfamiliar failure patterns the use of the Weibull distribution is not suitable for that. Despite these challenges, it is concluded that this research has substantial potential for future researchers to make decisions for complex systems in any field.

6.1 Future scope:

This study has the following future scope:

- The suggested Neutrosophic reliability framework with the UGF method is helpful to evaluate the reliability of many crucial subsystems like boiler, generator and turbine in the thermal power plant system.
- This study is useful to manage unknown and inconsistent failures in the system with the application of probabilistic distributions besides Weibull distribution for future studies.
- The combination of Sophisticated reliability models with Neutrosophic fuzzy methods can improve decision-making ability under uncertainty.

- This new methodology is suitable not only for the thermal power plant industry but can be extended in other different industries like manufacturing, plant, renewable energy etc.

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